

IMPROVEMENT OF LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT AND COMPRESSION-AFTER-IMPACT PERFORMANCE BY Z-FIBRE PINNING

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ABSTRACT: Z-fibre pinning is a new method of through-the-thickness reinforcement of laminated composites. This paper presents an experimental test and theoretical analysis on how and why these pins can improve the resistance to impact loading and damage tolerance under post-impact compression. Specimens were made of carbon/epoxy T300/914 with nominal thicknesses of 2, 4, and 6 mm. For the specimens tested in this study, z-pinning reduced impact damage area by 19-63% depending on the specimen thickness and impact energy. The CAI failure strains for the unpinned samples were about 0.6% while all the pinned strains were above 0.9%. If a factor of 1.5 were introduced to account for manufacturing differences and hot/wet performance of the laminate, a conservative design strain to failure limit would be 0.4% for the unpinned specimens and 0.6% for the pinned laminates. This indicates that the use of z-pins could increase the design strain limit from the currently accept level of 0.3-0.4%. All of these observations are discussed in the context of theoretical and numerical models that have been advanced to predict the critical impact force and z-pin performance in terms of laminate stiffness and the fracture toughness of mode-I delamination with the z-fibre bridging effect.

KEYWORDS: Z-pinning, impact, compression-after-impact (CAI), delamination, damage tolerance.

INTRODUCTION

Advanced carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRPs) have been widely used in the aerospace industry, and the application is going to increase rapidly in order to reduce the payload and hence to enhance the performance. However, the poor properties in the thickness direction (often referred as the z-direction) make CFRPs particularly susceptible to low velocity impact damage. This damage can be caused by dropping tools, parts being hit by runway debris, or flying through hailstorms. This impact damage is of particular concern because it is often barely visible. There may only be a small indent on the impacted face while significant delamination exists internally and significant cracking exists on the back face. Due to the nature of aircraft structures, the back face of the laminate is often in an area that is not easily accessible and thus the damage often goes undetected. This damage can seriously degrade the laminate's compressive strength. Because this damage often goes undetected, designers must allow for this barely visible impact damage (BVID) when design the component. A design strain-to-failure limit of 0.3-0.4% is currently used for aircraft compression panels while the undamaged material may be capable of strain limits of 1% or higher [1-3].

Two methods can be adopted to allow designers to use higher strain-to-failure limits and thus decrease the weight of the component. The first method is to improve detection of the damage. Adding more access panels to allow visual inspection of the back face is often unpractical due to the number of access panels required and their location on leading edges and flight controls. Detecting the damage using non-destructive testing such as c-scan or x-ray is also unpractical due to the amount of time

required for the testing, and the removal of component from the aircraft. The second method is to improve the through-thickness properties of the laminate in an attempt to reduce the accidental damage or to make the parts more damage tolerant under the service loads. Stitching or inserting short fibre rods in the z-direction have shown to greatly improve the fracture toughness. The recently developed Z-Fiber^{TM1} technique involves inserting metal pins or cured carbon fibre pins into the laminate through the laminate thickness, and it offers significant improvement in impact resistance, compression-after-impact (CAI) strength, and the ultimate strength of stiffener pull-off [4-6].

In this work, the influence of z-fibre pinning on low-velocity impact and compression-after-impact strength were investigated over a range of specimen thicknesses and impact energies to determine if the effectiveness of z-pinning is dependent on specimen thickness and impact energy. The impact tests were analysed in terms of the critical impact force and damage area. The CAI tests were discussed in the context of an FE model that simulates the increased fracture toughness of z-pinned laminates and the z-pin bridging effects.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Material and specimen preparation

Specimens were manufactured of carbon/epoxy T300/914 prepreg material with nominal thicknesses of 2, 4, and 6 mm. All specimens were 100 mm by 150 mm. All specimens had a quasi-isotropic lay-up sequence: $[0/+45/90/-45]_{2S}$ for the 2 mm panel, $[-45/0//+45/90]_{4S}$ for the 4 mm panel, and $[0/+45/90/-45]_{6S}$ for the 6 mm panel. Half of these specimens of each thickness were z-pinned with a pinned area of 50 x 50 mm, see Fig. 1. The Z-fibres were supplied by Aztex Inc. The pins are made of T300 carbon fibres embedded in bismaleimide (BMI) resin. In this study the areal density of z-pins is 2% that results in a distance of 1.75 mm between adjacent pins (measured from the centre of the pins).

2. Experimental procedures

All specimens were clamped at all edges and impacted at various impact energy levels (Table 1). After impact testing, selected specimens of the thickness of 4 and 6 mm were subjected to compression tests to determine their compression-after-impact (CAI) characteristics. Details of the impact and CAI tests are reported in [7], and the main results and analysis are given in the next section.

Fig. 1 Specimen dimensions and z-fibre reinforced area.

¹ Z-fiberTM is a registered trademark of Aztex Inc., Waltham, MA, USA.

Table 1. Impact test parameters.

Specimen Thickness (mm)	Total Drop Mass (Kg)	Impact Energy (J)	Drop Height (m)	Impact Velocity (m/s)
2	2.2	3	0.132	1.65
		5	0.230	2.13
4	4.7	15	0.324	2.52
		20	0.432	2.91
6	11.3	20	0.179	1.88
		30	0.268	2.30
		40	0.360	2.66

RESULTS & ANALYSIS

1. Resistance to impact damage

Table 2 contains the average damage area for all impact energies and all specimen thicknesses. The damage area for each individual specimen is plotted against the actual impact energy in Fig. 2.

As can be seen in Table 2 and Fig 2, all the pinned specimens had a smaller damage area than the unpinned specimens. For the 2 mm specimens impacted at 3-5 J, the pins reduced the damage area by 19-38%, and the effectiveness of the pins increased with the impact energy. For the 4 mm specimens impacted at 15 –20 J, the pins were much more effective at restricting the damage area reducing the damage area by 40-46%. The effectiveness of the pins also increased with the impact energy but the increase was not as great as for the 2 mm specimens. For the 6 mm specimens impacted at 20-40 J, the pins were even more effective at restricting the damage area than they were for the 4 mm specimens reducing the damage area by 58-64%. However, the effectiveness of the pins slightly decreased with the increasing impact energy.

As the thickness of the specimens increased, the pins became more effective. This is due to the change of the failure mode of the specimens. The 2 mm specimens fail more in bending than in transverse shear while the 6 mm specimens fail more in shear than in bending. The pins are more effective in shear than in bending and thus the more a specimen fails in shear, the more effective the pins will be.

Table 2. Impact test result - average damage area

Nominal Thickness (mm)	Nominal Impact Energy (J)	Unpinned Specimen Damage Area (mm ²)	Pinned Specimen Damage Area (mm ²)	Difference (%)
2	3 J	127 (±5)	103 (±12)	18.9
	5 J	307 (±16)	191 (±21)	37.8
4	15 J	917 (±64)	552 (±31)	39.8
	20 J	1382 (±92)	748 (±66)	45.9
6	20 J	1728 (±152)	629 (±19)	63.6
	30 J	2269 (±95)	848 (±28)	62.6
	40 J	2498 (±75)	1041 (±9)	58.3

The numbers in parentheses indicate standard deviation.

Fig. 2 Damage area versus impact energy.

2. Critical impact force, P_{crit}

The delamination area is normally plotted against the initial kinetic energy of the impactor. This energy is labelled the impact energy or incident energy. The damage area is minimal until a threshold value is reached. After this threshold value, the size of the delamination increases almost linearly with the impact energy until penetration occurs [8]. The threshold impact energy is an important characteristic; below this energy level, minimal damage is generated by the impact event. However, this threshold value of impact energy is hard to determine experimentally due to scatter, and it is also difficult for structural designers to use as a design parameter against impact damage. Several studies have indicated that damage is initiated when the impact force reaches a critical value [2, 9-10]. The critical impact force is the force required for damage initiation, indicated by the first drop in the impact force vs. time history graph (Fig. 3). Davies and Zhang have proposed the following equation for estimating the threshold value of the critical force [9]:

$$P_{crit} = \sqrt{\frac{8\pi^2 E t^3}{9(1-\nu^2)}} \cdot G_{IIc} \quad (1)$$

where, P_{crit} is the critical force for damage initiation, E the equivalent in-plane modulus of the laminate, ν the Poisson's ratio, t the laminate thickness, and G_{IIc} the mode II critical strain energy release rate. This shows that the critical force is proportional to $t^{3/2}$, which is verified by experimental results [8-10].

Previous test results with conventional unpinned laminates have shown that the critical force remains approximately constant after the onset of delamination [9]. Since P_{crit} depends only on the material properties and plate thickness and importantly is independent of the plate size and boundary conditions, it is possible to predict the behaviour of the plates under impact loading.

For the material used in this study, value of $G_{IIc} = 0.8 \text{ N mm}^{-1}$ was used, which was obtained for a similar material (HTA/6376) by the displacement-controlled end-loaded split beam test giving propagation values [11]. This value was also used for the z-pinned laminate to represent the critical fracture energy in a small cohesive zone at the delamination front. A recent study has found that the equivalent in-plane modulus of the laminate (E) for z-pinned plates is reduced by 7-10% due to z-pins

presence. Taking a quasi-isotropic modulus of $E = 60 \text{ GPa}$ for unpinned laminate, and $E = 54 \text{ GPa}$ for 2% pinned laminate [12], we find:

$$P_{crit} = 680t^{1.5} \quad (\text{Un-pinned laminate}) \quad (2a)$$

$$P_{crit} = 645t^{1.5} \quad (2\% \text{ z-pinned laminate}) \quad (2b)$$

Fig. 3 Definition of impact forces: critical, residual, and maximum force.

The calculated critical impact force values are indicated in Table 3 that are close enough to the experimentally measured critical forces to give confidence in predicting the onset of delamination for z-pinned laminates based on the critical contact forces. In some situations it may be decided that delamination is to be avoided at all cost; in which case Eq (1) is all that is needed for the threshold value of the P_{crit} , provided the critical force can be predicted or measured.

An observation from the test results (Table 3) is that the critical force was lower for the pinned specimens than for the unpinned specimens. A difference of 5-10% in the P_{crit} values between the z-pinned and unpinned laminates is predicted by Eq. (2). The reason for the lower critical force for the pinned laminate is due to the reduction in the equivalent in-plane modulus (E). Therefore for undamaged plates, pinned laminates are less stiff, hence lower P_{crit} values.

Table 3. Impact test result – average critical impact force values

Specimen Thickness (mm)	Impact Energy (J)	P_{crit} Experimental (Unpinned) (N)	P_{crit} Experimental (Pinned) (N)	Difference Expt (%)	P_{crit} Predicted (Unpinned) (N)	P_{crit} Predicted (Pinned) (N)
2	3	1616 ±72	1579 ±115	2.3	1920	1824
	5	1591 ±49	1569 ±18	1.4		
4	15	5355 ±215	4627 ±47	13.6	5440	5160
	20	4978 ±67	4510 ±153	9.4		
6	20	9556 ±390	8564 ±423	10.4	9990	9480
	30	9370 ±302	8319 ±583	11.2		
	40	9012 ±235	7740 ±209	14.1		

The force vs. time history gives better illustration of the differences between the unpinned and pinned specimens. A smooth trace indicates no damage to the specimen. Drops in the trace or truncated peak force indicate damage with the amount of damage being proportional to the height of the drop and the number of drops. Figure 4a shows the behaviour of the thinner plates (2 mm) with one sample pinned and one unpinned both impacted at 5J. Fig 4b shows the thicker plates (6 mm) impacted at 20J.

For the 2 mm specimen impacts, some low frequency noise was present. There were very few drops in the trace and the height of the drops was relatively small. This indicates little damage to the specimens, and the main damage was caused by matrix cracking due to bending. For the 5J impacts, the height of the pinned drops was slightly smaller than the height of the unpinned drops indicating that the pinned specimens was less damaged than the unpinned specimens.

Fig. 4a Force versus time history for 2 mm plates under 5 J impact energy.

Fig. 4b Force versus time history for 6 mm thick plates under 20 J impact energy.

For the 6 mm specimens, the impact event for the unpinned specimens lasted slightly longer than that of the pinned. This occurs because that after the initiation of delamination at $P=P_{crit}$ the pinned specimens were stiffer (due to much less damage propagation) compared to the unpinned specimens and therefore could recover faster from the impact event. The pinned specimens had a significantly smoother trace than the unpinned specimens. They also held a higher peak force after damage initiation indicating that the damage propagation was not as extensive as for the unpinned specimens. For all impact energies, the height of the force drops in pinned samples was much smaller than that of the unpinned. These drops were also less frequent for the pinned specimens. This was because the pinned specimens were significantly less damaged than the unpinned specimens.

For both pinned and unpinned specimens, the damage initiation force values were similar (within 5-10% difference). After damage initiation at $P=P_{crit}$, the subsequent damage growth was very different which was resisted by z-fibre bridging mechanics. Consequently, the damage areas of z-pinned laminates were much smaller although the damage was initiated at a lower critical force compared to the unpinned plates. The unpinned specimens would have little resistance to the delamination forces. However, this bridging effect under impact loading was not predicted by the study.

Increasing the pinned area until all the damage was contained within the pinned area marginally improved the impact performance of the specimens. For the 4 mm specimen impacted at 15J, the pinned specimens were 11.4 % less damaged than those impacted by Bitsianis [13]. For the same specimen impacted at 20 J, the pinned specimens were 14.0 % less damaged than results reported in [13].

3. Damage tolerance (CAI strength)

Only the 4 mm and 6 mm thick specimens were subjected to compression-after-impact testing. All specimens failed by delamination propagation caused by local buckling initiated from the impact damage. This local buckling mode is illustrated in Fig. 5. It took approximately 5 seconds from visible damage growth to the final failure for the unpinned specimens while it took over 30 seconds for the pinned specimens. The pinned specimens did not fail until the visible damage had extended to the entire width of the pinned area.

The average residual compressive strengths of the specimens are presented in Table 4. The individual residual compressive strengths as a function of impact energy are presented in Fig. 6. The pinned specimens all failed at approximately 45% higher stress than the unpinned specimens. The only exception was for the 6 mm thick specimens impacted at 20 J. This may be due to the fact that the pinned 6 mm specimens impacted at 20 J were the first specimens subjected to compression testing. The first two specimens tested were not clamped into the support with the same force as all the other specimens. If these two specimen results are removed, the difference between the pinned and unpinned results becomes 42%. All the unpinned strains were above 0.6% while all the pinned strains were above 0.9%. If a factor of 1.5 were introduced to account for manufacturing differences and hot/wet performance of the laminate, a conservative design strain to failure limit would be 0.4% for the unpinned specimens and 0.6% for the pinned specimens.

Fig. 5 Schematic of CAI test (side view) showing local buckling.

Table 4. Average residual compressive strength.

Specimen Thickness (mm)	Impact energy (J)	Unpinned Average Failure Stress (MPa)	Pinned Average Failure Stress (MPa)	Difference (%)
4	15	171 (± 16)	310 (± 23)	44.8
	20	153 (± 4)	285 (± 6)	46.3
6	20	223 (± 1)	342 (± 38)	34.8
	30	159 (± 17)	289 (± 18)	45.0
	40	140 (± 3)	252 (± 17)	44.4

The numbers in parentheses indicate standard deviation.

Fig. 6 Residual compressive strength vs. impact energy

4. Z-pin bridging effect in mode I delamination

The significant difference in residual compressive strength between the pinned and unpinned plates may be explained by two factors. Firstly, the impact damage area is considerably smaller for the pinned plates; hence the CAI strength of the pinned specimens will be higher. However, the difference in residual compressive strength remained relatively constant for all specimen thicknesses and all impact energies, at 42-45%, suggesting a second factor that is independent of the specimen thickness and impact damage size. We believe that it is the bridging mechanism offered by these z-pins that delay the growth of the delamination crack.

Since an anti-buckling guide was used during the CAI tests, there was no visible global buckling for this small coupon sample. Therefore, the post-impact compression test is dominated by the mode I interlaminar delamination fracture as illustrated in Fig. 5. There are studies on the bridging effects offered by through-thickness reinforcements, such as stitching [14] and z-pinning [15-16]. Our recent work on z-pinned double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens [16] has concluded that the effectiveness of z-pinning is mainly owing to the formation of a large scale bridging (LSB) zone behind the advancing crack front (Fig. 7). Once a delamination crack has propagated several millimetres into the z-fibre field, z-pins within the LSB zone will bridge the delamination crack; the LSB process can

stabilize or even temporally arrests the delamination crack. The mechanism of this bridging effect is the z-fibre pullout process during stable crack growth, which shields the delamination crack from the full delaminating loads by absorbing considerable amount of strain energy that otherwise would have been consumed for delamination growth.

The assumption made by the LEFM that all energy dissipations are included in the fracture energy and confined within a small zone of the damage front is not valid for z-pinned laminates. Our study [16] has shown that the irreversible energy dissipation due to z-pins pulling out is the dominant term in the energy balance equation and thus it enhances the fracture toughness of z-fibre reinforced laminates. With reference to the mode I delamination of the z-pinned laminate, define:

$$G_I = \frac{1}{B} \cdot \left(\frac{dW}{da} - \frac{dU_e}{da} \right), G_{IC} = \frac{1}{B} \frac{d\Gamma}{da}, \Phi_{ir} = \frac{1}{B} \cdot \frac{dU_{ir}}{da} \quad (3)$$

Where, G_I is the strain energy release rate due to applied force, G_{IC} the fracture toughness of the unpinned laminate (material property), and Φ_{ir} the energy dissipation rate due to the irreversible process of z-pins pulling out, which is the toughening mechanism of z-pinned laminates. Therefore, the Griffith fracture criterion for z-pinned laminates can be written as:

$$G_I = G_{IC} + \Phi_{ir} \quad (4)$$

Here the strain energy release rate G_I equals to the toughness of the z-pinned laminate during crack growth, which is the crack growth resistance. It is the increased fracture toughness ($G_{IC} + \Phi_{ir}$) that results in increased CAI strength for the z-pinned laminates. The term ($G_{IC} + \Phi_{ir}$) is a magnitude higher than G_{IC} [16]. Therefore z-pinning is very useful for damage tolerance design.

Fig. 7. FE model of a double-cantilever-beam (DCB) specimen [16].

CONCLUSIONS

Z-fibre pinning improves the impact performance. For all specimen thicknesses and impact energies, the pinned specimens were less damaged than the unpinned specimens. The pins were more effective for the thicker specimens. The effectiveness of the pins also increased with the impact energy.

Under low-velocity impact loading, the effectiveness of z-pins is in the crack propagation stage rather than the initiation stage.

Z-pinning also improves the compression-after-impact strength. The pinned specimens had an approximately 45% higher residual strength than the unpinned specimens. This difference in residual compressive strength remained relatively constant for all specimen thicknesses and all impact energies

indicating that the effectiveness of the z-pins in improving the CAI strength is independent of specimen thickness and impact energy, but dependent on the z-fibre bridging mechanism that is a function of z-pinning density and quality. All the pinned specimens had a higher failure strains than the unpinned specimens. This indicates that the use of z-fibres could increase the design strain limits for aircraft structures from the current level of 0.3-0.4 %.

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